

S3E Start

Open call text #1

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Document revision history

Version	Date	Description of change
v.1	26/10/2022	1 st version of Open Call Text
v.2	14/11/2022	Changes in the targeting of 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals
v.3	19/12/2022	Update the eligible countries, namely Kosovo, and figure 2.

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1 Introduction

S3E – Southern European Entrepreneurship Engine is a project, funded by the European Commission, focused on accelerating **deep tech projects, start-ups, and SMEs** that aim at providing solutions towards a more sustainable society and economy in line with Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)¹.

The S3E program is built around **three tracks** of carefully designed services tailored to support researchers, research teams, start-ups, scaleups and SMEs in advancing their technologies, products, processes, or services towards the market. Participants in the programs will be selected through open calls.

This document provides a full set of information useful for interested applicants who are willing to participate in **S3E Track 1: S3E Start**, that is directed towards research teams from research and development organizations (e.g., universities, research institutions, start-ups, or companies), and technology transfer officers. This document provides detailed information regarding the S3E Start program and its **first Open Call for Proposals** (also referred to as Open Call #1), as well as a general overview on the S3E project.

2 S3E overview

The **S3E – Southern European Entrepreneurship Engine** project mission is to develop an **engine of growth** that will contribute to improve the connectedness and efficiency of the **entrepreneurship ecosystems in southern European countries**.

S3E consortium partners are:

- **HiSeedTech** - A not-for-profit association founded by private companies that came together with the purpose of enabling the creation of value from knowledge through technology entrepreneurship and open innovation.
- **EPLO Institute for Sustainable Development** – part of an international organization dedicated to mainstreaming the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the EU Green Deal, providing capacity building, policy work and educational programs.
- **IDI** (International Development Ireland) specialises in practical day-to-day implementation for Government agencies in economies which are growing and changing rapidly
- **Australo** Interinnov Marketing Lab SI - is a marketing agency specializing in growth hacking for research and innovation.

¹ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

The S3E project is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 European innovation ecosystems under the grant agreement ID: 101072135 ([see here the Cordis fact sheet](#)).

S3E will focus on accelerating **deep tech projects, start-ups, and SMEs** that, by providing solutions towards a more sustainable society and economy, can impact social development and economic growth in these countries and contribute to the timely achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, in line with the EU Green Deal, the Recovery and Resilience Facility and the NextGenerationEU fund.

S3E will provide skills to researchers and technology transfer actors in science-based entrepreneurship and technology commercialization, supporting growth stage start-ups in business development and in procuring investment, and providing technology brokerage for corporates and scale-up stage start-ups and SMEs.

The program is built around **three tracks** of bespoke services tailored to start-ups' varying levels of maturity (i.e., early, growth, and scaling stages):

- **S3E Start:** For research teams and technology transfer offices, S3E offers a hands-on training program to hone their commercial skills and secure early funding for development.
- **S3E Charge:** For growth start-ups, S3E provides mentoring and networking to develop an investment-ready business plan and facilitate access to non-dilutable and dilutable funding
- **S3E Reverse:** For scaling start-ups and SMEs, S3E will set up an Open Innovation ecosystem to broker, connect and match corporates to scaling start-ups through a challenge-solution duality.

Figure 1. S3E Tracks

3 S3E Start at glance

3.1 Who is this program for?

S3E Start is designed for **research teams with deep tech projects**, grounded in a scientific discovery or meaningful engineering innovation, that want to explore the path from the lab to the market.

S3E Start is also for **technology transfer officers** that want to learn a thoroughly tested methodology to foster science-based entrepreneurship and technology commercialization.

3.2 What will you get from the program?

S3E Start is driven by an internationally proven process for technology commercialization that was specifically developed for deep-tech projects. The hands-on approach of the process guides the **research teams** in the development of a business case for a product, service or process grounded on the scientific discovery or engineering innovation with which the team applied to the Program. So, you will acquire skills in technology commercialisation and science-based entrepreneurship using your own project and the set of deliverables that, in each class, will be provided to the teams to guide you through the process. When you finish the Program, you will have developed a business case for a product, service or process developed from your research outcomes and you will have acquired skills to:

- link Science & Technology to product and market needs,
- better communicate science to a non-scientific audience,
- evaluate the different paths to move the technology to the market.

The outcome of S3E Start will also better position you to apply for public or private funding, because it will help you link your science to market needs and validate the assumptions that support the arguments to justify why you will be creating social and / or economic value.

Technology transfer officers will participate by joining a team and will learn the Program methodology through the same hands-on approach.

3.3 How is the program structured?

The starting point of the Program is a technology proposed (in the application form) by each participating research team. Over a **period of 18-weeks** research teams will receive **online training** that will help them understand the process required to develop a business case for a product (or service) grounded on the proposed technology (hour and a half every week), **webinars** on topics relevant to the development of the business case (one hour every two weeks) and **mentoring** (hour and a half every two weeks).

So, S3E Start offers you an 18-weeks hands-on experience that involves:

- **In-class tutorials**, mainly on the topics related to the process used to guide the participating teams in the development of a business case for a product, service, or process grounded on the proposed technology. Note: classes are held every week for one hour and a half.
- **Webinars**, on diverse topics pertinent to the development of the relevant skills (e.g. intellectual property, financials, business development, venture funding.). Note: a total of seven webinars (one hour long) will be held.
- **Mentoring** (industry experts) that will guide the teams on validation of the project and in the development of the business case. The mentors supporting the S3E Start edition are individuals who are somehow connected to the area of deep tech and entrepreneurship, and who are prepared to help teams solve problems that arise throughout the program. You can see an updated list of mentors on the S3E website (<https://south3e.eu>). Note: meetings with mentors last an hour and a half and are held every two weeks.
- **Networking** with industry leaders and showcase opportunities at the S3E Open day.

It is also important to mention that:

- The teams will undergo a training program that will have as the visible outcome a business case for a product/service or process concept sustained by the technology proposed.
- The teams will pitch their project, at S3E Open day, to pre-seed stage investors and corporate ventures.

The diagram below provides a more detailed look into the three phases of the S3E Start process:

Figure 2. S3E Start program approach

The approach used in the **S3E Start program will be highly iterative**; in the sense that as the teams amass information from the market, they may be required to iterate back to improve previous decisions and findings. The role of the mentors is crucial in this iterative process in forcing the teams to iterate back and select the best opportunities. At the end of the program there will be an **Open Day on the 20th of July 2023**.

In the table below, further details are provided about each step of the S3E Start program:

<p>IDEATION PHASE</p>	<p>In this phase a set of clearly defined product concepts will be developed and prioritized considering the linkages between the unique capabilities of the technologies and customer/market needs (Technology-Product-Market linkages). Each team is required to generate multiple product concepts that can be enabled by each technology. Then research teams will have to identify diverse market opportunities for each product concept to further specify product attributes.</p>
<p>DEVELOPMENT PHASE</p>	<p>In this phase teams will refine, improve, validate, and select among the product concepts devised in the 'ideation' phase using a guided approach that will force them to contact the 'market' to challenge and sustain each of the T-P-M linkages proposed in the ideation phase. In the early stages of this phase, teams will be looking for 'fatal flaws' (product or market) that will justify 'dumping' one (or more) T-P-M linkage(s). With the information gathered from the market teams will develop "value propositions" for their products using a standard format that will force them to (i) clearly define the product, (ii) tie customer needs to the benefits of using the product in economic terms and (iii) differentiate the product from competitors based on unique product features. Additionally, they will build a business model that, for the product moving forward, describes the rationale of how the company will create, deliver, and capture value. Throughout this phase participants will have to use a set of management tools (e.g., 5 Forces Analysis, SWOT Analysis, Industry Mapping, "Voice of the Customer", etc.) to gain a much better understanding of the way the market works and will be supported by the tools embedded in the approach, thus fine-tuning their product concept choices.</p>
<p>COMMERCIALIZATION PHASE</p>	<p>In this phase teams put the pieces of the puzzle together by building a strategy to bring the product to market. This phase begins with the definitions of the pricing point and the sales plan answering strategic questions such as market traction and market entry point(s). Additionally, drawing on the business model previously designed teams will define their development roadmap that will allow them to build the financial projections and risk analysis. At this stage teams will have all the elements needed to produce a business case and a final pitch that will be the final deliverables for the Program.</p>

Table 1. S3E Start stages

4 Open Call #1

S3E Start is launching its first open call for applications.

S3E Start call is open to research teams from Southern European countries² with deep tech projects, grounded in a scientific discovery or meaningful engineering innovation, that want to explore the path from the lab to the market. Projects in the following scientific fields will be considered: agricultural sciences, engineering and technology, medical and health sciences, and natural sciences.

The projects must envisage an economic and social impact, targeting the following Sustainable Development Goals:

- **No Poverty (SDG 1):** End poverty in all its forms everywhere.
- **Zero Hunger (SDG 2):** End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture.
- **Good Health and Well-Being (SDG 3):** Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages.
- **Quality Education (SDG 4):** Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.
- **Gender Equality (SDG 5):** Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls.
- **Clean Water and Sanitation (SDG 6):** Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all.
- **Affordable and Clean Energy (SDG 7):** Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy for all.
- **Decent Work and Economic Growth (SDG 8):** Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all.
- **Industry Innovation and Infrastructure (SDG 9):** Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation.
- **Reduced Inequalities (SDG 10):** Reduce inequality within and among countries.
- **Sustainable Cities and Communities (SDG 11):** Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable.
- **Responsible consumption and production (SDG 12):** Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns
- **Climate Action (SDG 13):** Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.
- **Life below water (SDG 14):** Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas, and marine resources for sustainable development.

² For the scope of S3E, Southern European countries include the following European countries: Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Cyprus, Romania, Slovenia, and Spain. And the following Associated countries: Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia, Kosovo, and Turkey.

- **Life on land (SDG 15):** Protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.
- **Peace, justice, and strong Institutions (SDG 16):** Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels.
- **Partnership for the goals (SDG 17):** Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development.

S3E Start call is also open to technology transfer officers from Southern European countries that want to learn a thoroughly tested methodology to foster science-based entrepreneurship and technology commercialization.

The S3E Start Open Call #1 was launched on the **7th of November 2022 (12:00 CET)** and will last until the **10th of February 2023 at 17:00 CET**. Regardless of the number of applications, a maximum of **25 research teams** and **20 technology transfer officers** will be selected.

Selected projects will be announced on the 7th of March 2023 and the program will start on the 21st of March 2023 lasting until the 20th of July 2023.

The F6S platform will be the entry point for all proposals' submissions to S3E Open Calls, which is directly linked from S3E website (<https://south3e.eu/>). Submissions received by any other channel and after the open call deadline will be automatically discarded.

To support applicants, **S3E Start will organize four Q&A Webinars** on the following dates:

- 24th of November 2022 at 9:30 CET
- 7th of December 2022 at 14:00 CET
- 17th of January 2023 at 9:30 CET
- 7th of February 2023 at 14:00 CET

Save your place at <https://south3e.eu/>

For the application form and detailed guidance for applicants, please download the files available at the <https://south3e.eu> website.

5 Support material

For updated information on S3E, in general, and S3E Start, in particular, please check out our website (<https://south3e.eu/>), follow our social media accounts³ or subscribe to our Newsletter.

³ Follow us on LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/south3e/mycompany/> and Twitter: <https://twitter.com/south3e>

Privacy Policy available at: <https://south3e.eu/privacy-policy/>

Open call #1 support material:

- **S33 Start - Open Call #1 Text**, this document.
- **S3E Start Guidelines for Applicants**, which sets out the guidelines for participation in the first open call for proposals of the S3E Start project.

For other needs, please contact the [Help Desk](#).

